

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

STORM FAQ AND TROUBLESHOOTING

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1 INTRODUCTION

This document is addressed to Site Administrators responsible for StoRM installation and configuration.

2 FAQs

2.1 GENERAL INFORMATION

Q. How can I communicate issues to the StoRM team?

A. Please use the GGUS helpdesk (<https://ggus.org/pages/home.php>) and provide the following information:

- Your Site Name
- A description of the problem
- The version of the StoRM packages installed
- The type of the StoRM deployment
- Any relevant log file

For other issues you can contact StoRM support (storm-support@lists.infn.it), or StoRM user (storm-users@cnaf.infn.it).

Q. Where can I find the StoRM System Administration Guide?

A. You can find the StoRM System Administration Guide document in the StoRM Documentation page (<http://storm.forge.cnaf.infn.it/documentation/home>).

Q. Where can I find the StoRM FAQ?

A. You can find the StoRM FAQ document in the StoRM Documentation page (<http://storm.forge.cnaf.infn.it/documentation/home>).

Q. Where can I find the StoRM Functional Description?

A. You can find the StoRM Functional Description document in the StoRM Documentation page (<http://storm.forge.cnaf.infn.it/documentation/home>).

2.2 RELATED TO FRONTEND

Q. Where are the Frontend log files located?

A. The Frontend log files are located under `/var/log/storm/`

Q. What are the Frontend configuration files?

A. The Frontend configuration file is `storm-frontend-server.conf` located under `/etc/storm/frontend-server`.

Q. What are the other configuration files to consider in a Frontend node?

A. It is useful to look at the content of the `/etc/hosts` and `site.def` files.

Q. What are the mandatory checks?

A. In the Frontend configuration file check the contents of the following parameters:

```
fe.threadpool.threads.number  
db.host  
db.passwd  
db.user  
be.xmlrpc.host
```

verifying the correctness of the backend hostname, user and password of database. Moreover, verify that the file `/etc/hosts` be well-formed.

2.3 RELATED TO BACKEND

Q. Where are the Backend log files located?

A. The Backend log files are located under `/var/log/storm/`

Q. What are the Backend configuration files?

A. The Backend configuration files are `storm.properties`, `namespace.xml`, and `logging.xml` located under `/etc/storm/backend-server`.

Q. What are the other configuration files to consider in a Backend node?

A. It is useful to look at the content of the `/etc/hosts`, `/etc/my.conf`, `/etc/fstab` and `site.def` files.

Q. What are the mandatory checks?

2.4 RELATED TO GRIDFTP

Q. Is GridFTP able to calculate checksum?

A. Yes, it is.

Q. What type of checksum algorithm is supported by GridFTP plugin?

A. The type of checksum algorithm supported by the GridFTP plugin is `adler32`.

Q. Where are the GridFTP log files located?

A. The GridFTP log files are located under `/var/log/storm/`

Q. What are the other configuration files to consider in a GridFTP node?

A. It is useful to look at the content of the `/etc/hosts` and `site.def` files.

Q. What are the mandatory checks?

2.5 RELATED TO GRIDHTTPTS

2.6 RELATED TO CHECKSUM

Q. In which case is the Checksum service useful to be configured?

A. When your application needs to calculate checksum of files that are already on the storage but they do not have checksum.

Q. Where are the Checksum log files located?

A. The Checksum log files are located under `/var/log/storm/`

Q. What are the Checksum configuration files?

A. The Checksum configuration file is `storm-checksum-server` under `/etc/storm/checksum-server`.

2.7 RELATED TO STORM-CLIENT

2.8 TROUBLESHOOTING STORM